

When the construction of police legitimacy backfires? Emotion expression management in times of the erosion of the rule of law

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Abstract Emotion management in relation to police legitimacy during the pandemic in Poland offers an illustrative case study of backfire mechanisms in times of the erosion of the rule of law. Grounded in social constructionism, the study uses qualitative frame analysis to determine: what emotion management strategies embedded in discursive frames were used by the police and the state to build and rebuild police legitimacy during the pandemic? Why did they backfire? Masking, a strategy negative in valence, backfired. Ignoring emotions experienced by officers in frames constructed to gain legitimacy widened the rift between police and ordinary people. For the latter, it was equivalent to losing another public institution to the ruling state. If masking is the only strategy in use, law enforcement will likely be perceived negatively, and citizens will resist, impairing the ability of the police to perform its duties.

Introduction

Successful European post-communist democracies have been facing a progressive decline in democratic characteristics since the financial crisis of 2008 (Bochsler and Juon, 2020). During a recent public health crisis, governments expanded executive power, restricted citizens' fundamental rights, developed state surveillance, weakened opposition groups, and strengthened their political power (Anisin, 2022). The result is a re-emergence of pre-pandemic protests aimed at, for example, democratic backsliding, public sector mismanagement, corruption, electoral manipulation, and police brutality (Gerbaudo, 2020). Moreover, protesters opposed public health measures introduced to limit virus transmission, inadequate or failed governmental responses to the

pandemic, and unwieldy health systems. People took to the streets despite civil freedom restrictions, ignoring health risks. Waves of protests challenged the stability and legitimacy of governments and political regimes across the globe (Pleyers, 2020). At the same time, the opposition failed to reverse democratic backsliding or stop authoritarian consolidation (Gidengil *et al.*, 2022).

The governments of post-communist states with authoritarian histories of policing and military repression once again turned to their violent legacy to avert the breakdown of authoritarian structures that could come from both organized resistance and ordinary citizens, whose non-compliance evolved into protests (Gerschewski, 2013). Nevertheless, since repression was too costly to maintain stability in the long run, governments were forced to

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create legitimacy understood as ‘the right to exercise power’ (Tankebe, 2013). As these changes unfolded quite quickly in Poland, the country offers an instructive look into the way they occurred in post-communist European countries. It is helpful to comprehend the mechanisms of police legitimacy construction under the erosion of the rule of law. Police legitimacy is the belief that the police are authorized to call on the public to obey the law, and the public is obliged to cooperate with the police. It translates into the public’s confidence and trust in the police (Tyler, 2004, p. 86).

At the early stages of the public health crisis, Daniel D. Jones pointed to the impacts of pandemic policing on police legitimacy. As soon as the police were afforded additional powers to enforce fast-changing laws and bylaws, it became clear how this would impact their legitimacy (Jones, 2020). Besides regular law enforcement duties, officers needed to perform duties related to crisis management (e.g. enforcing stay-at-home and social distancing orders). Police legitimacy ensured the efficient implementation of these tasks in cooperation with citizens. On the other hand, as the rule of law eroded this meant law enforcement was also used to stabilize autocratic rule threatened by protesters and opposition (Kostić and Bošković, 2020). Legitimacy was necessary for police to efficiently perform their order-maintenance role, enforce the law, and ensure the stability of political systems, be it democracy or autocracy, without resorting to repression (Tyler, 2004; Tankebe, 2013). Legitimacy is closely related to efficient governance as public trust in law enforcement directly translates into trust in the law in general (Bottoms and Tankebe, 2012). Therefore, it is crucial for police and their state supporters to understand the social consequences of police legitimacy and their role in constructing it (Bonner and Dammert, 2022).

When intensified communication efforts aimed at generating police legitimacy proved to be inefficient or even counterproductive, a considerable challenge for these entities became apparent. Hence the puzzle: what circumstances cause police legitimacy to backfire? This article directs scholarly attention to emotion expression management within the interpretive frames used to construct police legitimacy in the context of rule of law erosion. The main

argument is that emotion expression mismanagement is a condition under which creating police legitimacy has the opposite result from the one intended.

Managing the expression of emotions while constructing police legitimacy during the COVID-19 pandemic in Poland offers an illustrative case study. A few turning points took place in a short time, altering the development of police legitimacy. The hitherto upward trend was reversed, and public protest were followed by a sharp decline in police legitimacy. The reasons behind it seem clear. However, it is unclear why the ongoing reconstruction of police legitimacy was unsuccessful despite increased communication efforts to gain public trust. By drawing upon the Polish case, this paper aims to explain this backfire mechanism.

Background

Among post-communist countries, the Polish police is a model of successful transition from an authoritarian to a democratic law enforcement service. Since 1990, Polish police have strived to regain public trust. Relationship between citizens and law enforcement was strained during the communist period of the Polish People’s Republic (PPR). Owing to a successful fight with organized crime, negotiated management as a protest policing model, preventive actions, and information campaigns, Polish law enforcement in the last decade have enjoyed a relatively high level of trust. Polls placed it at the forefront of best-rated public institutions (Kościńska, 2021). Nevertheless, in 2020, police faced a dramatic decline in terms of its public reception—by 20.1 percentage points. In 2021, it lost a further five percentage points (Kołczyńska, 2022). A 2020 survey by the Market and Social Research Institute indicated that 44.1% of Poles vested trust in Polish law enforcement. In a survey by the same institution in September 2017, 64.2% of Poles expressed confidence in the police. Other surveys confirm that the public trust rate was stable in 2017–2019 (Demagog, 2020). In a relatively short time, from the onset of the pandemic till the lifting of restrictions (March 12, 2020, to May 16, 2022) it appears law enforcement have squandered reputational gains of the last 20 years.

Following pandemic-related restrictions, police are accused of applying the unconstitutionally imposed regulations too overzealously, making pointless interventions (e.g. patrolling woodlands and preventing people from entering open-air spaces), being extremely brutal or idle, and indiscriminately using force during anti-government protests. Non-governmental organizations documented instances of unequal treatment of pro- and anti-government assembly participants, unlawful arrests, as well as cases of Parliament Members being pepper sprayed or plainclothes officers brutally dispersing crowds. These situations translated into diminishing confidence in the police (Kościńska, 2021).

Consequently, this leads to more people voicing their discontent. Extreme expressions of resistance included hate crimes and direct threats against law enforcement officers and their families. The police were labelled as the PiS Militia (PiS—Prawo i Sprawiedliwość, Law and Justice, the ruling party) and compared to the Motorized Reserves of the Citizens' Militia (ZOMO), or Citizens' Militia (MO), the PPR national police organization. These law enforcement services were utterly subordinated to the ruling communist party until it transitioned from a communist state to a liberal democratic political system in 1989. Furthermore, Poles created and distributed internet memes highly critical of the police, Facebook photo filters with police officers imposing fines on users, and burlesque Tik Tok parodies (Rak, 2022).

At the same time, the police and its state supporters made joint efforts to generate, maintain, and rebuild police legitimacy. They knew it was crucial in order to prevent widespread insurgency as 70% of Poles supported the anti-government protest movement inspired by the Women's Strike protests (Kielczykowska, 2021).

This study investigates: What strategies of emotion management embedded in discursive frames were used by the Polish police and their state supporters to rebuild police legitimacy during the pandemic? Why did they backfire? The case study utilizes critical instances of how police and their state supporters manage expressions of emotions while constructing police legitimacy. The focus is on interpretative frames used to account for police

action during critical events. A case study approach provides an appropriate way to address this question because it enables researchers to delve analytically into a vital phenomenon of iatrogenic misconstruction of police legitimacy that has yet to be examined in depth.

Literature review and theoretical framework

The study combines the social psychological theory of police legitimacy and the social constructionism approach to establish a consistent and comprehensive theoretical framework for analysis. From the former, it derives a conceptualization of police legitimacy, while the latter offers a theoretical lens to understand its construction. Social psychologists expose constantly created support for police as legal authorities and a perceived duty to be obedient. They highlight the public's judgments on the rightfulness of police conduct and the institutions controlling it as the first pillar of political legitimacy. The second is the perceived obligation to act on police orders based on internalized obedience to authority (Tyler, 2004; Worden and McLean, 2017, p. 482). The study draws upon Tom R. Tyler's social psychological definition of police legitimacy that builds on the pillars of trust and obligation. It means the belief that the police are authorized to call on the public to obey the law, and the public is obliged to cooperate with the police, which translates into the public's confidence and trust in the police (Tyler, 2004, p. 86).

Originating from the sociology of emotions, the social constructionist approach to emotions is widely used in social movement studies to explain social mobilization and demobilization. It enables researchers to trace emotion trajectories of political engagement, determine which emotions transform individuals previously uninterested in politics into activists or prompt disengaged movement participants to re-engage or change supported values and views (Ellefsen and Sandberg, 2022). However, it is neglected in studies on the construction of police legitimacy despite its indisputable potential to explain the social dynamics resulting from emotion management (Worden and McLean, 2017). This study seeks to expand on the literature by providing

empirical evidence to support an argument that some strategies of emotion management used in the service of building police legitimacy may backfire.

Inspired by Erving Goffman's classic works on the strategic and conscious management of emotions, Arlie Hochschild (1979) proposed an emotion-management perspective as a theoretical lens for examining how people attempt to manage feelings. Its major category is emotion management, understood as 'the act of trying to change in degree or quality an emotion or feeling' (Hochschild, 1979, p. 561). Importantly, it covers not the outcome of 'emotion work' but the effort that can be successful or not. Mismanagement or failed management acts still uncover formulations that shaped the effort (Hochschild, 1979). This approach reveals how emotions are liable to be changed and affected by society. Catherine Theodosius (2006) advanced Hochschild's approach by identifying interactive, relational, and unconscious emotion processes in management. An analysis including those processes can develop our comprehension of emotions beyond cognition.

Hochschild differentiated between two strategies of emotion management: evocation and suppression. While the cognitive focus of the former is on eliciting a desired feeling that is absent at first, the latter is on preventing an already active, undesired feeling (Hochschild, 1979). Drawing upon this seminal observation, Paul Ekman and Wallace V. Friesen (1975) offered a more detailed typology that covers simulation, inhibition, intensification, deintensification, and masking. Simulation occurs when no emotion is experienced and consists of displaying an emotion that is not felt. Inhibition is pretending that there is no emotion despite feeling an emotion. Intensification involves creating an impression that emotions are stronger than they really are while deintensification is the opposite. Finally, masking refers to displaying one emotion while feeling a different one (Hayes and Metts, 2008). Differentiating between the relationships between experienced and displayed emotions, these strategies allow researchers to investigate conscious and unconscious attempts to shape one's perception.

Although expressions of emotions embedded in frames encourage citizens to perceive the police in expected ways, they do not determine perception

(Bonner and Dammert, 2022). As Hochschild argues, emotion management becomes an object of awareness when a managing subject's feelings do not align with the situation, that is, the event itself does not explain the subject's emotions. Emotion management backfires when there is no tripartite consistency between situation, conventional frame, and expressed feeling (Hochschild, 1979). Accordingly, conscious use of above-mentioned strategies to manage emotion expression in accord with normative expectations relevant to the situation may translate into achieving interactional, relational, professional, and self-presentational goals (Hayes and Metts, 2008).

Javette Grace Hayes and Sandra Metts (2008) advance the theory of emotion management by identifying which strategies are positive and negative in valence. It provides a theoretical grounding for hypotheses. First, emotions expressed through simulating and intensifying are significantly more positive in valence than those manifested through inhibiting or deintensifying. Second, masking emotions, that is, hiding them, is substantially more negative in valence than exhibiting emotions that are felt. Strategies positive in valence are conducive to achieving goals, whereas strategies negative in valence result in failure or backfire.

Methods and data

Grounded in the social psychological theory of police legitimacy and the social constructionism approach, the study uses qualitative frame analysis to address the following questions: What were the strategies of emotion management embedded in discursive frames the Polish police and their state supporters used to rebuild police legitimacy during the pandemic? Why did they backfire?

A discursive frame is an interpretative schema that outlines situations by simplifying them, so it becomes easier to comprehend (Bonner and Dammert, 2022). This study concentrates on frames used to justify police actions during three events considered critical junctures in constructing police legitimacy. Those are the Strike of Business Owners (May 7–20, 2020), the 2020–2021 Women's Strike protests (October 22, 2020–January 29, 2021), and the celebration of the 12th anniversary of the

Smoleńsk catastrophe (April 10–13, 2022) (Rak, 2021). During and after them, the level of confidence in the police dropped by leaps and bounds.

I analyzed materials distributed to construct police legitimacy to identify discursive frames. Then, I juxtaposed them with policing narratives presented by police officers confidentially. It allowed me to determine the similarities and differences between emotion expressions created for the needs of police legitimacy construction in the public sphere and the emotions felt during the situations. In other words, the juxtaposition enabled me to discover emotion management strategies.

First, the corpus of sources includes the Polish Police Headquarters (Polska Policja: @PolskaPolicja: $n = 29$ tweets) and the Warsaw Police Headquarters' official Twitter profiles (Policja Warszawa: @Policja_KSP: $n = 393$ tweets), which is a whole population of tweets used by the police during the critical junctures. The former released tweets on behalf of the Polish Police, centralized and organized under the central command in the capital city. Commenting on the police' and protesters' activities on an ongoing basis, they constructed police legitimacy. Twitter profiles gave access to primary official statements on police activity and played a crucial role in disseminating how police viewed order policing. Furthermore, journalists treated these verified accounts as reliable sources providing law enforcement's perspective on unfolding events (Drapała, 2020). Omitted are other social media due to their insignificant share in constructing police legitimacy (no reference to police engagement in policing order during critical junctures).

In Poland, the number of Twitter users and coverage increased. In 2020, 5.8 million Poles used Twitter, in 2021—8.6 million, and in 2022—11 million. The coverage grew from 21.5% in 2020 to 36% in 2021 and 37% in 2022 (Wojtas, 2020; TW, 2021, 2022). Twitter is the second most popular social media in Poland. Only Facebook is more popular, but it serves Poles to seek support and promote charity collections. In turn, Twitter is a place to exchange opinions on political issues (Szutiak, 2021). Still, ordinary people rarely use Twitter to exchange opinions and interact with the police and other state institutions. Like in other post-communist states, Twitter works as 'a platform for elite

communication' (Matuszewski and Szabó, 2019, p. 11). It serves those institutions to communicate their position, which is later widely disseminated through traditional media and intra-elite communication (Popiołek *et al.*, 2021, p. 92).

The engagement rate on Twitter is the most important indicator of Twitter performance since it counts public interactions. It rests on likes, retweets, quotes, and replies, which are all public metrics Twitter provides. The engagement rate is 'calculated as the sum of: (Likes + Retweets + Quotes + Replies) divided by the number of tweets, then by the total number of followers, then multiplied by 100' (Mention, 2022). According to the Twitter Engagement Calculator, the average engagement rate is 0.01% for @PolskaPolicja and 0.042% for @Policja_KSP. On average, Polska Policja gets 11.9 likes per tweet, 0.9 replies per tweet, and 3.1 retweets per tweet. Policja Warszawa receives 11.3 likes per tweet, 0.1 replies per tweet, and 1.8 retweets per tweet (Mention, 2022). While the Polish Police Headquarters' Twitter profile has 163,000 followers, the Warsaw Police Headquarters' profile has 31,600 followers.

During the three critical junctures, police messages were more often contested than further disseminated on Twitter. Moreover, instead of engaging in a substantive discussion, the commentators of police tweets mocked police action (e.g. in the comment of June 19, 2021, 'So, no one died, phew, another "success" of MO'), accused the police of being subordinate to PiS (e.g. in the tweet of October 11, 2021, 'The threat to society is you militiamen at the service of PiS; 'political police commissioned by PiS'). Comments often did not address tweets directly but criticized the Polish police or PiS (Rak, 2022, p. 20). Accordingly, retweets and comments are not an authoritative account of information about the effectiveness of police communication efforts among Poles. As such, they are beyond the scope of analysis.

Second, the corpus of sources includes a whole population of materials disseminated by TVP Info news ($n = 1,873$) as representing the efforts of state police supporters in creating police legitimacy. Since PiS passed a media law, which brought public broadcasting under direct government regulation, public media are subordinate to

the government. As such, they care about police legitimacy, give voice to its selected creators, and accurately present official police announcements and officers' comments. According to the [Institute for Media Monitoring \(2020\)](#), TVP Info was the most opinion-forming public media during critical events.

Data collection starts with identifying all excerpts from the corpus of sources that explain and support police actions during critical junctures. They are indicative of expressed feelings and juxtaposed with those felt during the situations. To identify the latter, that is, emotions involved in a situation but not necessarily expressed in public by the police and their supporters, I conducted 36 in-depth interviews with policemen engaged in order policing during critical junctures. After refusals to provide information on protest policing, it was impossible to carry out official interviews with a representative sample. Therefore, the study benefits from exponential non-discriminative snowball sampling. The first subjects were recruited among police officers who were part-time doctoral students at the research project host institution. They provided multiple referrals, and the latter then provided further ones until the accounts merely duplicated what their predecessors had already told up to the point where theoretical saturation was gained, in other words, until new data stops delivering exemplifications of new theoretical elements but rather confirms what has already been determined ([Punch, 2014](#), p. 134). Personal engagement in at least one of the three critical junctures was a primary selection criterion. It allowed me to learn about feelings associated with interactions with assembly participants and law enforcement. Interviews lasted an average of 10 min and took place 1–5 days after the event finished to capture emotions inherently tied to the situations, not affected by media coverage or other factors. Officers were invited to describe their feelings during the situations. Questions were designed to elicit descriptions of emotions felt while enforcing order.

To classify and code emotions, the study follows the principle of inductive thematic analysis ([Ellefsen and Sandberg, 2022](#)). It rests on Hayes and Metts's classification framework that consists of ten emotion clusters named for the most critical emotions

in each cluster: 'Anger (anger, hate, disgust, and rage), Sadness (sadness, depression, sympathy, hurt, and disappointment), Happiness (happiness, joy, pride, hope, amusement, and excitement), Affection (affection, liking/attraction, caring, gratitude, and love), Surprise (surprise and shock/disbelief), Jealousy (jealousy and envy), Frustration, Fear (fear and worry), Guilt (guilt, remorse, and embarrassment), and Other (interest, aloof, confusion, pain, and pacifism)' ([Hayes and Metts, 2008](#), p. 384).

Following Michelle D. [Bonner's and Lucia Dammert's \(2022\)](#) design for counting frames, one excerpt delivering a whole idea of expressed feelings was counted as a single expression regardless of the number of sentences or words contained. If the idea recurs in a tweet, news, or interview, it still counts as one. This counting does not aim to measure the intensity of emotions precisely but to identify the configurations of expressed emotions.

The next step includes listing the emotions expressed in public with those involved in the situations. To reiterate: masking refers to displaying one emotion while feeling a different one; inhibition is pretending that there is no emotion or a particular emotion is not experienced despite feeling an emotion to neutralize the valence of expression; intensification involves giving the appearance emotions are felt stronger than they are, deintensification creates the appearance strong emotions are less intense; simulation is displaying an emotion not genuinely felt during the situation ([Hayes and Metts, 2008](#); [Rostomyan, 2013](#)). The use of strategies is interpreted through the theoretical lens to account for those processes of building and rebuilding police legitimacy that backfired.

The 2020 Strike of Business Owners

The Strike of Business Owners is a wave of protests organized by presidential candidate Paweł Tanajno (competitor to the incumbent president supported by PiS) and the Facebook group Strike of Business Owners. On May 7, 2020, entrepreneurs gathered at the Dmowski Roundabout in Warsaw, and at night they assembled in front of the Prime Minister's Office. The police dispersed the assembly and fined participants for not respecting social distancing regulations ([Szymczak, 2020](#)).

In the service of building police legitimacy, law enforcement and state media employed Anger (anger, rage, and disgust), Sadness (sadness and hurt), Affection (caring), and Happiness (excitement and pride). Anger and hurt emerged in police statements about strike participants, who supposedly gathered illegally and physically resisted police officers. Protest behaviour was equated with 'ordinary street banditry' (@Policja_KSP, 2020b). As law enforcement officers' lives were supposedly in danger, they were justified in their use of force, even if it led to spontaneous bursts of rage directed at protesting opposition members or journalists. Critical media accounts were brushed off by the police as a 'complete distortion of the actual course of events,' 'fake news,' and 'manipulation' (@Policja_KSP, 2020a). Rage co-occurred with disgust, understood as a strong feeling of disapproval and dislike of protesters (ignoring the ban on assemblies and police orders).

Once evidence shed more light on the proceedings, and it became apparent protesters were indeed physically abused, sadness came to the fore. It was not, however, an expression of regret related to a denial of committed abuses, but rather an offshoot of anger over the aggressive behaviour of protesters toward officers.

Law enforcement took pride in their efforts to curb the spread of the pandemic. They enthusiastically described their new duties, be it enforcing stay-at-home orders or providing security, as examples of community service. Polish law enforcement reported it had secured hundreds of assemblies and reacted to legal violations swiftly and accordingly.

It is worth noting the strike occurred at the beginning of the pandemic when little was known about the deadly coronavirus. As a result, during interviews, police officers expressed Fear (fear and worry) and Other (confusion). The former took the form of fear of contracting the virus and putting family members at risk. It was expressed by almost all interviewees. Police officers were most concerned that they would unconsciously, despite maintaining safety rules, cause a serious illness, or death of the elderly, children, and relatives dealing with pre-existing conditions. A few officers admitted worrying about their health and life. The others

referred to the risk inherent in their profession and a dedication to serving the community. Protesters' aggression underlying the construction of police legitimacy was not a cause of fear.

Secondly, all police officers expressed confusion at double legal standards. The government unconstitutionally banned civil freedoms of assembly and speech, however, the limitation applied only to anti-government gatherings since the new Law on Assemblies states that gatherings organized by public authorities are state gatherings. As such, they were allowed when public gatherings were prohibited to limit the spread of the virus. Police officers were aware that they treated citizens unfairly. The incumbent president and the politicians of the ruling party freely organized meetings with voters. At the same time, counter-candidates, including the leader of the Strike of Business Owners, were punished with severe financial penalties, and stigmatized by the police and state media as criminals. The confusion was also evident in the statements about a lack of clearly determined detention procedures related to pandemic-induced regulations and resulting doubts about dealing with participants of assemblies. Police officers felt unprepared to supervise assemblies that might have influenced political results.

The juxtaposition of emotions manifested in public with those involved in policing the Strike of Business Owners reveals a complex masking strategy, which changed gradually over time (Table 1). By managing emotions, police changed the quality of felt emotions. The police displayed Anger (anger, rage, and disgust), Sadness (sadness and hurt), Affection (caring), and Happiness (excitement and pride) while feeling Fear (fear and worry) and Other (confusion). The construction of police legitimacy that rests on hiding emotions, which is negative in valence, is likely to backfire. The police reacted very quickly to strike-related events on Twitter accounts and in TVP statements. The state media immediately picked up on Twitter's narrative and adopted police strategies for emotion management. Additionally, state media provided a platform for police spokespersons and pro-government journalists. The latter's task was to use their own authority to strengthen police legitimacy (since

2015, it has been common practice for journalists from other media to act as experts instead of field experts). The speed with which specific events were commented on and the ruthless effort to generate police legitimacy came at the expense of a coherent, fact-based and well-thought-out emotion management strategy.

The Women's Strike protests

The largest wave of protests in democratic Poland started on October 22, 2020, when activists took to the streets to oppose a judgment of the Constitutional Tribunal, dominated by judges appointed by and subordinated to PiS (Kubicki, 2022, p. 254). The judgment imposed stringent anti-abortion legislation, making almost all cases of abortion illegal. It raises concerns over the safety of women, deprived of a possibility to terminate pregnancy even in cases of incurable foetal illness or conditions threatening the mother's life. On the night of January 27, 2021, the judgment of the Constitutional Tribunal went into force, and quickly afterward, protests ended despite unresolved grievances (Polynczuk-Alenius, 2022).

Over time, the events that caused excitement routinized and police statements became devoid of enthusiasm. The police constructed their legitimacy with Anger (anger and rage), Affection (caring), and Happiness (pride). As was the case of the Business Owner Strike, law enforcement displayed caring in the description of actions taken to ensure public safety. Moreover, police continued to express pride in their role and cited their readiness to risk their own lives to protect others during the time of the pandemic.

Anger was a reaction to unsteady cooperation between citizens and police, which resulted from declining legitimacy. Furthermore, anger went hand in hand with expressions of helplessness as police voiced their disappointment at people breaking sanitary restrictions and participating in illegal assemblies.

Anger reached an extreme form of rage when public figures, independent media journalists, opposition politicians, or detainees' lawyers expressed opinions that contradicted the police and presented different interpretations of the law or events. TVP

Info reflected and strengthened the police's frames and illustrated them with journalists' and police spokespersons' comments.

The interviewed police officers expressed Sadness (sadness and hurt), Fear (fear and worry), and Other (confusion). As many as 31 officers felt sad and hurt by the accusations of politicized protest policing and favouring the ruling party. First, friends put pressure on officers to 'take off their uniforms' and join protesters to protect Polish women's reproductive rights. Second, protesters demanded the police take sides by shouting 'come with us', as members of 'Solidarity' shouted to the Citizen's Militia in undemocratic Poland. As they ignored these calls, protesters called officers 'traitors' and the Citizens' Militia. Moral dilemmas and contradictory messages from other people and various media caused a feeling of confusion among all officers.

In sum, 31 officers experienced fear. Contrary to the onset of the pandemic, officers no longer feared contracting the virus, with only 2 expressing continued concern. This time, 29 officers feared that protesters might have been right and that, after the law was changed, the life of their wives, girlfriends, mothers, and sisters could be put at risk if medical assistance was limited. 11 officers worried about their perception in the local community and among friends. Since they did not join protesters, they worried about being identified with the ruling party's supporters. Nevertheless, the will to stay on duty was stronger than worries and fears.

The juxtaposition of emotions expressed in public with those involved in policing the Women's Strike protests shows the use of masking (Table 1). However, it was much less complex than masking at the pandemic's beginning and did not change over time. The shift in the quality of emotions that were felt drew upon manifestations of Anger (anger and rage), Affection (caring), and Happiness (pride) while feeling Sadness (sadness and hurt), Fear (fear and worry), and Other (confusion). A strategy negative in valence likely to backfire.

The 12th anniversary of the Smoleńsk catastrophe

The celebration of the 12th anniversary of the Smoleńsk catastrophe aimed to commemorate 96

Table 1: Emotions expressed by the police, their state supporters, and experienced by officers

Type of emotion	Emotion	@PolskaPolicja n = 29 tweets	@Policja_KSP n = 393 tweets	TVP Info n = 1,973 news	Police officers n = 36
Anger	Anger	CJ1: 4 CJ2: 3 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 72 CJ2: 308 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 513 CJ2: 1211 CJ3: 0	
	Disgust		CJ1: 16 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 87 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	
	Rage	CJ1: 2 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 21 CJ2: 232 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 464 CJ2: 361 CJ3: 0	
Sadness	Sadness	CJ1: 1 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 6 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 8 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 0 CJ2: 31 CJ3: 4
	Hurt	CJ1: 1 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 6 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 8 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 0 CJ2: 31 CJ3: 0
	Disappointment				CJ1: 0 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 4
Happiness	Pride	CJ1: 8 CJ2: 6 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 29 CJ2: 54 CJ3: 1	CJ1: 31 CJ2: 3 CJ3: 3	
	Excitement	CJ1: 1 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 23 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 465 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 0	
Affection	Caring	CJ1: 6 CJ2: 11 CJ3: 0	CJ1: 32 CJ2: 294 CJ3: 1	CJ1: 46 CJ2: 998 CJ3: 7	
Frustration	Frustration				CJ1: 0 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 36
Fear	Fear				CJ1: 8 CJ2: 31 CJ3: 0
	Worry				CJ1: 6 CJ2: 11 CJ3: 0
Guilt	Embarrassment				CJ1: 0 CJ2: 0 CJ3: 2
Other	Confusion				CJ1: 9 CJ2: 36 CJ3: 0

A number of emotion expressions during the critical junctures (CJ):

CJ1: The Strike of Business Owners.

CJ2: The Women's Strike protests.

CJ3: The 12th anniversary of the Smoleńsk catastrophe.

Source: own study.

public figures who died on April 10, 2010. Among the victims of the plane crash was the twin brother of PiS's leader, the president of Poland, Lech Kaczyński. State institutions, PiS politicians, and

their supporters spread conspiracy theories which framed the Russians and opposition figures as responsible for the crash and subsequent cover up (TVP Info, 2022).

Over the years, this event was the subject of political disputes, prompting demonstrations and counterdemonstrations. It even motivated a change in the Law on Assemblies to privilege those held by the government. After Russia invaded Ukraine, an increase in hostility toward Russia was to be expected. As a result, excessive police mobilization was carried out to secure the Smoleńsk anniversary and accompanying events.

Nevertheless, contrary to expectations of the ruling elite, interest in the political dispute and conspiracy theories waned. The transformation of human tragedy into a political dispute meant that there was no feasible ground for genuine sadness to be expressed on a social level. Above all, however, Poles were concerned about the crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border, the development of the Russian-Ukrainian war, helping refugees from Ukraine, and the impact these events have on everyday life. On the level of emotion management, sadness did not appear in the messages of the police, nor was it expressed by police officers.

On the contrary, on Twitter, Happiness (pride) and Affection (caring) dominated. The former was reflected in the expressions of pride in being responsible for providing public order and security during numerous important events, including public gatherings. As law enforcement stressed time and time again, they essentially took care and safeguarded citizens. TVP Info did not give the floor to journalists or police officers. Only journalists' comments confirmed the social media messaging of law enforcement.

The primary emotion expressed by all interviewed police officers was Frustration mixed with Sadness (sadness and disappointment) and Guilt (embarrassment). They were brought to Warsaw from all over Poland to secure a public assembly. They answered the call despite a prevailing sense they were more needed somewhere else, like the Polish-Belarusian border, the site of hybrid warfare involving refugees. Moreover, police officers felt redundant as their numbers were significantly larger than necessary. Regular citizens often behaved derisively toward law enforcement, feeling public funds were being wasted. Many officers were brought to the capital just to police the assembly and hence felt out of touch with the locals. Two

officers were embarrassed about the situation, and the rest insisted that they had carried out orders and were on duty.

Only four officers expressed sadness and disappointment at the fact there were no riots there were supposed to control. Additionally, they believed that the plan to secure the public assembly rested on forecasts of mass mobilization against the ruling party.

The juxtaposition of emotions expressed in public with those involved in policing the anniversary events reveals how emotion management was deployed to impact the quality of emotions (Table 1). Once again, the only strategy in use was masking. The police displayed Happiness (pride) and Affection (caring) while feeling Frustration, Sadness (sadness and disappointment), and Guilt (embarrassment). Hiding emotions is significantly more negative in valence than exhibiting emotions that are felt, and it translates into a negative valence-based construction of police legitimacy that was likely to backfire.

Discussion

The preliminary study provides initial empirical evidence to support the theory-grounded hypothesis that masking, as a strategy negative in valence, resulted in the construction of police legitimacy that backfired. Starting with the Strike of Business Owners, police legitimacy has declined. This strategy caused a division in social consciousness between 'them', that is, the police supporting the rulers, and 'us'. The same emotion management strategy used during successive phases of political contestation favoured the deepening of this division. It was a turning point regarding the perception of the police, as it showed the distance between the public perception of events, the situation, and the point of view of law enforcement. The emotions inherent in constructing police legitimacy were deemed socially inappropriate for the situation. At the same time, officers' feelings found no outlet in the official discourse. Emotions experienced by officers did not differ from those prevailing in Polish society at that time. Nevertheless, their omission in frames constructed to gain police legitimacy increased the distance between the police and

ordinary people. For the public, this was tantamount to forfeiting another state institution to the ruling party and thus another manifestation of the erosion of democracy. The order introduced under false narrative frames was treated as the actual limitation of the rule of law and pursuing the political interests of the rulers under the guise of keeping the rules of the sanitary regime. From that moment on, law enforcement in Poland has faced a deep crisis. Accused of being political and partial, police officers are losing trust. In the public discourse about protest policing, it has become common to refer to the militia of the PPR undemocratic era. If masking is the only strategy for managing emotions, the police will likely be perceived negatively, and their right to perform the order-maintenance role will be challenged.

Evidently, after violent protests with public display of police use of excessive force, trust in police declined in general, which is confirmed by independent and independently conducted public opinion surveys (Demagog, 2020; Kołczyńska, 2022). Before the transition in 1989, ZOMO units were clearly distinguished in the collective consciousness from the other police services of MO. Although this paramilitary police formation was created to police mass events, fight the most dangerous criminals, and help in case of crises (e.g. natural disasters), it served mainly to suppress protests. The repressive and lethal model of escalated force used exclusively by the ZOMO resulted in a low level of trust in this unit. However, after the transition to democracy, the Polish Police has been functioning in the collective consciousness as a homogeneous and internally undifferentiated unit, despite being composed of criminal, investigative, preventive, internal affairs, counter-terrorist, cybercrime, and support services. As a result, the activities of riot police are commonly generalized and referred to the police as a whole, which affects other areas of police work (Czapska *et al.*, 2014).

The article focuses on generating police legitimacy, while a study of the effects of generational attempts can be a valuable supplement. This research perspective raises a new challenge of integrating theories of generating police legitimacy with those uncovering under what conditions

legitimacy-generation attempts are efficient and resonate with the public's current beliefs. Besides, such theoretical foundations inspire new research questions about the effects of emotion management strategies when misinterpreted and read in different contexts.

Another challenge for future research on generating police legitimacy is to isolate the individual factors' influence on the legitimacy state and changes over time. The research assumption about the impact of communication originates from the adopted theoretical framework. However, it is worth considering combining research on communication efforts and direct community-police contact as coexisting pillars for legitimacy to restore or grow. On the one hand, far more people read police statements online or watch them on TV news than interact with police officers in person (Intravia *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, direct contact may lead to much more enduring beliefs about the police's authority and affect the internalization of obedience to authority (Graziano and Gauthier, 2018). Moreover, the narrative resulting from face-to-face contact can resonate within the social groups to which the person belongs. The effects of resonance depend on, for example, context, narrative, narrator, and audience (Worden and McLean, 2017). It poses the challenge of constantly monitoring the consequences of direct community-police contact, as surveys carried out after a particular time may provide distorted data. For instance, they may reveal opinions formed as a result of information about the last concrete action of police officers or vicarious experience with police rather than past personal experience.

Finally, the skilful management of emotions with the strategy of intensifying based on genuinely felt emotions, which is positive in valence, can be used to rebuild police legitimacy. In times of rule of law erosion, when the message results from subordination to the government, it is important to manage emotions in such a way that will help protect the public order while specific political goals are being pursued. While inept emotional management during order policing was not the most important factor that led to a decline in police legitimacy, it cannot be ignored as a condition of the decline. The backfire mechanism makes it possible to understand the

mistakes made when communicating with citizens. The lessons learned from this analysis are valuable to any state police force that has been faced with the need to explain their engagement in order policing. It is also a valuable lesson for all entities involved in building police legitimacy. It shows that ill-considered commenting on events, often subordinate to political interest, may be counterproductive, especially when genuine emotions are concealed. Skilful emotion management can protect police legitimacy when the police are politicized and subordinate to an authoritarian government.

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